

**A SET OF EXERCISES ON TEACHING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS
AND VOCABULARY CONSTRUCTIONS**

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the study of the English phraseology units and typology of two languages which presents a certain interest both for theoretical investigation and for practical usage.

Key words: prescriptive, phraseological, feedback, reassuringly, sympathize, practice activities, frustration.

We should use different types of methods during teaching classes. And we can use majority of modern techniques while teaching phraseological units and vocabulary.

Schools and institutions One of our problems was to sort out the real from the illusory in this area. A lot was made by the publishers of the fact that the main book had to be the right length, there had to be so many units, so many pages per unit - linked to so many hours of work, the syllabus had to include this and that grammatical item, there had to be tests. And yet when it came to it our instincts told us that there was a lot more freedom in our market to do what we liked in terms of overall structure, providing our material was usable and motivating for the level of students. This was confirmed when we talked to teachers informally. Indeed many teachers seemed not to notice how many pages there were in a unit or what was in the syllabus! [2, pp16-18]

Institutional needs nevertheless imposed perfectly proper constraints on our writing: the material should not be inappropriate to the context, the topics should be

interesting to their students, the material should not date, it should be 'user-friendly', it should be usable alongside and sometimes integrated with other materials and should enable students to make rapid progress. On the production side it should be good quality but cheap and all components –coursebook, workbook, tapes, teacher's book - should be available locally on launch!

Teachers We felt teachers wanted a book they could sympathize with in terms of its pedagogic principles. It would need to have a fresh and original feel to it and yet be reassuringly familiar. At the same time teachers are very busy and they naturally wanted an easy life: not too much preparation, usable and motivating materials, fun activities that worked in terms of improving the students' communicative skills, transparent methodology, up-front grammar and a flexible approach which allowed teachers to use the materials more as a resource than a prescriptive course.^[1,30]

Students would want material that they could enjoy and in which they could find things they could identify with and learn from. Language needed to be comprehensible but there did need to be 'new' language there on the page. They needed a lot of revision, a lot of material they could use to study on their own. They needed supplementary material-such as workbooks.

Principles compromised With all these factors at work it is not surprising that the issue of compromise was central to our work. Having said that it is surprising how many of our grand principles above more or less survived. The main areas of compromise were these:

Overall structure

It was clear that the idea of a flexible course book was not (at that time) fully understood by our potential users. We were aware from initial feedback that some teachers felt they had to cover everything in the book in the order presented. Our idea of using the Workbook as part of the classroom resource was not universally accepted since many students did not have access to the Workbook. In other words the material ended up being less flexibly organised than we would have liked. However, at that time it is true that we were not sufficiently aware of the potential

of the Teacher's Book to go beyond declaring intentions and suggesting ideas to providing its own resources in terms of extra photocopiable practice activities - a situation we remedied in later editions. This facility very visibly puts into practice the principle of aiming to supply teachers with a resource to help them build up *their* programme. [3]

Originally we wanted to start the book with a 'deep-end' approach and so we flagged our first four units as review units - to activate language students had already been presented with and do remedial work on it if necessary. But many markets did not like or understand this approach and wanted straightforward presentation of the main language items. Should we have compromised and provided this presentation?

Lack of space caused us great frustration at the editing stage when we saw many of our practice activities disappear or get pruned. We had to make a decision whether to cut whole activities or cut back on the number of items within an activity. The fault was probably ours for having too great an ambition for too few pages. So the compromises that were made met with some complaints from users and we have had to provide extra material in the Teacher's Book in later editions.

Methodology

We did manage to get away from a traditional approach in terms of Unit structure since we started each unit with a skills activity rather than a language presentation but our original ambition to draw target language out of authentic texts failed at the intermediate level, partly because of the difficulty of finding texts which contained clear examples of the focus language together with interesting content. We got nearer our ambition at the upper-intermediate level.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

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